

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE STRATEGIC IMPORTANCE OF THE REVIVAL OF THE CITY OF SHUSHA IN STRENGTHENING THE STATE SOVEREIGNTY OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article examines the strategic importance of the revival of the city of Shusha in strengthening the state sovereignty of Azerbaijan. The strategic role and function of the restoration of post-conflict territories are substantiated. The multiplicative effect of the city of Shusha in accelerating the socio-economic development of Karabakh is considered. The processes of creating the housing stock of the city of Shusha and commissioning other social and production infrastructure facilities are analyzed. The historical and modern significance of the city of Shusha as an ancient cultural center of Azerbaijan is explained. The issues of using the city's tourism potential are highlighted. The goals of developing a green economy in Shusha and green energy infrastructure in the Karabakh economic region in general are given. Generalizations are made and proposals are made on the strategic importance of the revival of the city of Shusha in strengthening the state independence of Azerbaijan in the future.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh economic region, Shusha city, state sovereignty, strategic importance of the revival of Shusha city, development prospects of Shusha city, green economy, green energy, post-conflict territories.

The 21st century is remembered for quite significant events for the independent State of Azerbaijan. The Great Karabakh Victory, which began on September 27, 2020 and lasted 44 days, should be noted as a significant historical event. It was as a result of this victory that the trampled pride of the Azerbaijani people was restored, and our sacred and precious lands, including Shusha, were cleansed from the filthy feet of the occupiers. The occupiers were brought to their knees, and the Armenian leadership signed an act of surrender. Thus, Azerbaijan ensured its territorial integrity as an independent state and immediately began the revival of the territories liberated from occupation. It is no coincidence that the head of state noted at the Shusha Global Media Forum held on July 21, 2023 that, of course, the restoration of Shusha has begun, the Master Plan was approved some time ago, and now the first housing project is being implemented. You can see them in several places in the city. Within the framework of these projects, Shusha residents will return to their homes again. In addition, as I have already mentioned, Shusha was declared the cultural capital of Azerbaijan by the presidential decree, and our expectation is that we will have numerous guests from all over the world, there will be an influx of people. Because this is a rare, unique place. History, culture, architecture and climate form a unity here. This is our great wealth. Of course, this city is built on a rock, it is an ancient city, and it is truly the pearl of the Caucasus and the crown of Karabakh [1]. It is impossible not to agree with these opinions. Nature has not spared anything from Shusha, and at the same time, Shusha has its own unique features and characteristics, and if we consider historical aspects, Shusha's strategic importance increases many times over.

Shusha city has become one of the important trade centers of the entire South Caucasus since the end of

the 18th century. Shusha city gained fame with its handicraft products. At the beginning of the 19th century, a large army of craftsmen specialized in more than 50 fields of art operated in the city. At the beginning of the 19th century, 500 weaving looms producing various types of fabrics were operating here. The rapid development of capitalist relations led to the rise of silk production in Shusha to the level of factory-factory production. Life was in full swing in Shusha until the 20s of the 20th century [2]. All this can be considered as signs of Shusha's glorious and balanced historical and economic development. Shusha also fulfilled its historical function as the center of the Karabakh region, and today Shusha is considered the beating heart of the mentioned region. In fact, the revival and development of this city means the intensification of the socio-economic development of the newly created Karabakh economic region, which has regained its historical-geographical position and structure as a whole [3].

It should be noted that the development processes, demographic trends, and economic construction issues of Shusha are quite unique. If in the 19th century Shusha developed rapidly as the center of Karabakh, in the 20th century these processes were artificially hindered. Thus, with the support of the USSR leadership, Armenian nationalists and their supporters purposefully achieved the deprivation of Shusha from the status of the center of Karabakh. After the establishment of Soviet rule, Shusha was determined as the Center of the newly created Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Region. However, from July 7, 1923, Khankendi was chosen as the center of this region. Thus, Shusha was deprived of the function of being the administrative center of Karabakh [4]. It was during the Soviet period that dark clouds began to gather over Shusha, the population decreased several times, and neglect of the city's development increased.

Only since the early 1970s has the importance of developing the city of Shusha been brought to the fore, and the historical services of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev were made in these processes. Heydar Aliyev visited Shusha many times and personally participated in the opening of many facilities. He took important steps towards restoring Shusha's historical image and its status as the center of Karabakh. It was on his initiative that a resort complex was developed in Shusha and social infrastructure was strengthened, hotels and multi-storey residential buildings were put into operation, monuments were restored and new ones were created [5]. Shusha also performs a very important function as a cultural center of historical and strategic importance for our country. The monuments, cultural samples, house museums of prominent Azerbaijani artists and thinkers located here can be considered as cultural pearls [6].

It should be noted that the revival of the city of Shusha is currently the driving force behind the large-scale construction work being carried out in the Karabakh economic region. The city has created the impression of a construction site, repair and restoration work is being carried out on all sides, and on the other hand, a new social and service infrastructure is being created, and a network of facilities is being put into operation. Complex work is being carried out for the return of former internally displaced persons to their native lands [7]. The above is of great importance in terms of accelerating the socio-economic development of the city of Shusha, forming the sectoral economic structure of the city, and determining priority areas of activity. Many foreign experts and at the same time local experts, researchers, as well as the author of this study, prefer the idea that the elements of the cultural economy, various sectors of the service sector, and primarily tourism and recreation activities should occupy an important place in the economic construction of the city of Shusha. In our opinion, there are serious historical, economic, geographical, and climatic factors for this [8]. At the same time, the rapid revival of the city of Shusha, the formation of the urban economy, the creation of a network of hotels and service establishments, and in the near future the rapid construction of residential areas for the return of the first former internally displaced persons to the city, the construction of schools and hospitals, etc. factors create additional motivations for the recovery and revival processes in the region as a whole [9].

The development of the economy of the city of Shusha requires the emergence of new approaches, especially ensuring urban development based on high and "smart" technologies. Thus, currently, the mobilization of intellectual resources in Shusha, the application of high technologies in the creation of the aforementioned economic sectors can significantly accelerate the socio-economic revival of the city. These, in turn, can be viewed as a new peak in the progress of Azerbaijan as a strong state and play a serious role in the transition to a new stage of socio-economic development [10]. For this, it is necessary to take measures to increase the investment attractiveness of the city. It is known that the state has taken comprehensive measures to accelerate

the restoration and revival of the territories liberated from occupation. At the same time, various tax breaks and other incentive mechanisms have been applied. There are also incentives for those participating in these processes. But along with all this, we believe that one of the main priorities is to form alternative financial and investment sources in addition to state resources in construction and revival measures, and to prepare functional financial support mechanisms. In this regard, one of the important priorities is to create a maximum favorable investment environment for the effectiveness of the work to be done as a whole and to facilitate the attraction of foreign investments in these processes, and to ensure the participation of foreign investors [11]. Investment attraction mechanisms must be functional, the legislative framework must comply with international practice, and relevant factors must be seriously studied and taken into account to protect the interests of investors in return for the investments made. In general, it is necessary to intensify the processes of effective investment in the liberated territories and to take additional measures for this purpose [12]. The intensive economic development of a city of strategic importance such as Shusha, the parallel holding of various important international events in the city, and the constant increase in the number of local and foreign visitors to the city have created the need to maximize the acceleration of the construction and revival measures. On the other hand, the numerous transport projects implemented in the region are factors that can strongly increase the strategic role of Shusha. The implemented projects, the two international airports put into operation (Fuzuli and Zangilan International Airports), and the rapid continuation of the construction of a third international airport in the Lachin region, which has a complex relief, will allow a significant increase in the number of local and foreign tourists visiting Shusha in the coming years [13].

We would like to draw special attention to one historical event. The city of Shusha has also gone down in history as an impregnable fortress and is a symbol of heroism and courage of our people. Therefore, the socio-economic revival of the city of Shusha means an increase in the power of independent Azerbaijan in the long term. On the other hand, the Shusha Declaration, which raised Azerbaijan-Turkey brotherhood and alliance to an unprecedented level, is among the events of strategic historical importance. This will also be of serious importance in the unification of the geography of the Turkic world, in the rapid integration of the Turkic states that have been separated from each other for many centuries. The processes taking place among the Turkic-speaking states in this regard already give reason to say that in the coming years we will be able to see the closer integration relations of the Turkic-speaking states. In all these processes, the city of Shusha performs a unifying and stimulating function. At the same time, the "I State Program on the Great Return to the Liberated Territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan" was approved by the decree of the President of the country dated November 16, 2022 [14]. This program envisages large-scale restoration and revival projects and measures. We believe that the implementation of

the mentioned program will further accelerate the socio-economic development of the city of Shusha and enhance the strategic role of the city in the region.

It should be noted that since the beginning of the 19th century, the role of the city of Shusha in the Caucasus and in the region in general has increased significantly. Already in the first half of the 19th century, the number of caravan flows from Russia to Shusha had increased considerably. In particular, merchants from Derbent came to Shusha with great enthusiasm, where they bought a lot of silk, paint, etc., as well as weapons, mahud cloth, and other products. Shusha also played an important function in relations with South Azerbaijan. Merchants came to Shusha from various regions of the Ottoman Empire, and Shusha played a leading role in the formation of trade relations with European countries and India. In Shusha, those who stood out most in the development of the city, the construction of new neighborhoods, the construction of craft facilities, and related areas of activity were, of course, primarily the craftsmen who were engaged in crafts here. That is, shoemakers, carpenters, tailors, hatters, but weaving was more noticeable.

In the first half of the 19th century, there were looms in Shusha that produced various textile products, that is, capitalist relations were already developing in Shusha. Various types of art formed the economy of Shusha at that time. Sericulture was especially strongly developed in Shusha, and in the second half of the 19th century, there were several small silk workshops and factories in the city, as well as silk-dyeing factories. The specialization in silk in the region took place in Shusha, and in connection with the development of sericulture, people from other provinces and regions of Azerbaijan actively came here. In particular, silk raw materials from Sheki were brought here and processed. At the same time, carpet production developed here, carpets reflecting national ornaments were quite attractive, and merchants from other countries and continents of the world willingly bought these carpets and took them to other countries, and looms and individual carpet masters were growing here for the production of carpet products. The development of various dyeing products and crafts in Shusha was also noteworthy.

At the end of the 19th century, Shusha was already a fairly developed city as the administrative center of Karabakh, and the development of industrial enterprises here also attracted attention. Shusha was a developed cultural center of Azerbaijan, and the development of Azerbaijani oriental ornaments, mugham art and national music, and the creation of cultural and educational institutions accelerated here. At that time, various fields of art in Shusha embarked on their intensive development path. Theaters were created, and at the same time, the construction of a theater building was provided in Shusha, and theatrical performances were held here. On the other hand, a lot of work was being done in Shusha for the development of the ancient art of singing, and in the second half of the 19th century, councils and various associations operated here in connection with the development of the ancient art of singing in Azerbaijan, and music halls were built. At that time, all this allowed the formation of the initial

images of the cultural economy and the creation of basic elements. The creation of such enterprises, craft and cultural institutions in the city was of great importance for the protection of our national values and the upbringing of national artists. In the second half of the 19th century, the development of the khanende activity in Shusha, especially the intensity and popularity of theatrical performances in Tbilisi and Shusha, led to a great leap in the development of culture here.

Already at the end of the 19th century, many art and literary councils were operating in Shusha, and in particular, the Majlisi Uns literary poetry council under the leadership of Khurshudbanu Natavan played a major role. At the beginning of the 20th century, Shusha was of great strategic importance as both a cultural and recreational center of the region, as well as the main administrative center of Karabakh. The developed infrastructure here was also characteristic of that period. There were hotels, cultural objects decorated with national ornaments. Theatrical performances and musical institutions were operating. At that time, life in Shusha was almost boiling and developing. Horse racing competitions were held on the Jidiru plain, and Isa spring became one of the most popular places for people to relax. Thus, it can be noted that life in Shusha developed significantly at the beginning of the 20th century.

In the period before the collapse of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, guests and merchants came to Shusha from all over, including from distant countries, as well as from Turkey, Iran, various regions of Asia, and Russia. The development of Shusha also meant the development of Karabakh and Azerbaijan. At that time, a large number of artistic examples, cultural and historical monuments were being formed and becoming famous. As a result of these, Shusha gave the world outstanding artists who introduced the Azerbaijani people, and also played an important role in the development of national culture, contributing to the formation of the most valuable examples of our national culture and art in this regard. The monuments and features in Shusha are considered to be among the pearls that the Azerbaijani people will present to the world today.

It is precisely today that they can be effectively used in the formation of Shusha's economy. Shusha was also the center of Karabakh, people came here from all sides, new cultural objects and buildings in Shusha attracted attention. Associations in various creative and musical directions operated. In particular, due to the expansion of trade relations and the purchase and sale of various products, Shusha was one of the places where traders came with great enthusiasm. In addition, the city's charming nature, clean air, and the unique development features of Shusha were noteworthy.

During the former USSR, many enterprises were established in Shusha and work was done to ensure the socio-economic development of Shusha. First of all, it was very difficult to use the opportunities available in Shusha and to protect cultural monuments. The Bolsheviks, who dealt a heavy blow to the ancient customs and traditions of Azerbaijan, the activities of intellectuals and artists, were indifferent to the cultural heritage and existence of Shusha, and issues related to ancient customs and traditions. Mosques were closed and their

purpose was changed, most of the customs and traditions were banned, the calls of the intelligentsia in this direction were not taken into account and, as mentioned, they were either exiled or killed. As a result of all this, the development of Shusha until the 40s of the 20th century was not so fast and the city experienced certain problems. There were difficulties in protecting the cultural heritage of Shusha and indifference was shown to many monuments, and very little financial resources were allocated for the implementation of the measures necessary for that period.

After our lands were liberated from occupation, construction work began. The organization of post-conflict territories on conceptual grounds was ensured [15]. First of all, approaches based on the strength and economic power of our state were put forward. Decrees and orders were issued for the head of state to personally visit each occupied and liberated territory, assess the real situation there, and carry out revival measures, and purposeful allocation of funds began. At the same time, the clearance of mines from the liberated territories was accelerated and the revival of post-conflict territories began [16]. New economic regions were created, and the development drivers of the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions were identified in a comprehensive manner [17].

Hotels are also being built in the Karabakh region to create living opportunities. Hotels built in the city of Shusha, in particular, have many opportunities to provide high-quality service. Conference halls, meeting rooms, restaurants, shops, parking lots, and other necessary infrastructure facilities are available to guests. Shusha Castle – Shusha is considered one of the most beautiful regions of Azerbaijan and the cultural center of Karabakh. During the Karabakh Khanate (1747-1822), a fortress was built in the city of Shusha for defensive purposes between 1750 and 1751. This fortress was named “Panahabad” in honor of Panahali Khan, and later became known as “Shusha Fortress”. The fortress, one of the beautiful examples of Azerbaijani architecture, was built in the style of the Arran architectural school. Built using local stones and lime-egg mixture, the fortress has three gates. Govhar Agha and Aghdam Mosques – Another important cultural asset of Shusha is the Govhar Agha Mosque. There are two similar mosques called the Yukhari and Ashaghi Govhar Agha Mosques. These mosques are also among the landmarks symbolizing Shusha culture. The Yukhari Govhar Agha Mosque is the oldest mosque located in the central square of Shusha and was financed by Govhar Agha in 1883. For this reason, the mosque was named after Govhar Agha, the daughter of Karabakh Khan Ibrahim Khalil. It was registered as a historical and cultural monument of state importance by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Lower Govhar Agha Mosque was built in 1874-1875 and has architectural features of the same period. The architect of both mosques is Karbalayi Safikhan Karabakh. Both mosques are among the important buildings symbolizing Shusha culture. After the Second Karabakh War, reconstruction works are continuing rapidly in the region. In this context, large-scale

reconstruction and restoration works have been completed at the Upper Govhar Agha Mosque.

The main development impulses and drivers in these processes stem from the revival of the city of Shusha. The transformation of the city of Shusha into a construction site and, at the same time, the formation of socio-economic development infrastructure, the rapid construction of social facilities and the development of the service sector have a multiplicative effect on the economic development of Karabakh as a whole [18]. For this purpose, measures should be taken to increase the investment attractiveness of the region and special investment programs should be adopted [19]. At the same time, financial mechanisms should be applied to attract more economic entities and potential investors in the processes of accelerating the restoration work carried out in the Karabakh economic region and a flexible banking infrastructure should be created [20]. Along with this, in order to accelerate the processes of forming the green economy infrastructure of the region, first of all, the reserves of green energy resources should be assessed and the processes of creating the appropriate infrastructure should be intensified [21; 22]. In general, the measures taken will allow the formation and development of a new regional socio-economic development model in the regional policy of Azerbaijan [23].

Thus, taking into account short and long-term goals, we have summarized a number of points in terms of accelerating the revival of the city of Shusha and intensifying economic development:

- As restoration and revival measures accelerate, Shusha's status as the center of Karabakh is being fully established;
- Based on the revival projects carried out, it can be confidently stated that Shusha will become one of the most attractive cities not only in the region but also in the world in the near future;
- Taking into account its historical and modern strategic importance, Shusha will assume special importance as the city of unity of world Azerbaijanis and the cultural center of the Turkic states;
- Shusha is acquiring new strategic importance as the center of Karabakh and plays a multiplicative role in accelerating construction work in Karabakh;
- The implementation of support projects related to the city of Shusha, the construction of the Victory Road, the restoration of hundreds of large and small historical monuments and cultural centers in Shusha, and the taking of intensive measures for the rapid development of service areas, while ensuring the economic construction of the city, have a positive impact on the socio-economic development of the Karabakh economic region in general;
- The creation of high and “smart” technology-based service areas in the city of Shusha, the formation of education and healthcare infrastructure, and the construction of residential areas will in the near future turn the city of Shusha into one of the most attractive cities not only in the South Caucasus but also in the whole world, and will create additional opportunities for the reintegration of Karabakh into the country's economy

and the further increase of our country's influence at the international level;

– The revival of the city of Shusha will perform important functions and ultimately create additional opportunities for the strengthening of Azerbaijan's state sovereignty, etc.

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